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DORA - Door to Door Information for Air Travelers

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Abstract

In DORA project an intermodal door to door information system for air passengers is developed which is aimed at reducing the overall travel time for European air travels. This paper gives an overview on the added value of the DORA in comparison to existing door to door information services and describes the approach on how the DORA system is implemented in order to provide end-users with suitable mobility and routing information based on real-time data. To improve passenger orientation at the airports, waiting time detection and indoor positioning technologies are installed at the test-site terminals and integrated in the overall information system. It is shown how the whole system or single components can be easily integrated in third-party applications and transferred to additional cities by providing an open, scalable, and distributed system architecture. The diverse value generation of the DORA system furthermore leads to different business models which are discussed.

Keywords:

Intermodal Information Services, Seamless Air Mobility, Door to Door Mobility Information

1. Introduction

DORA is a research and innovation project funded by the European Commission in the framework of Horizon 2020 addressing the call MG1.3-2014: Seamless Air Mobility. The 3 year project, which started in June 2015, brings together a European expert consortium of airport operators, industry partners, transport operators, academia, and public authorities.

1.1 Objectives

DORA project aims at the design and the implementation of a seamless and integrated information system that helps air travellers to optimise travel time from the origin to the final destination of their trip. In order to reduce the overall travel time of a typical European air travel, the DORA system integrates travel information for the journey to and from the airport, for the processes inside the terminal buildings and the flight itself and provides this combined information in a single point of

visualisation to the air traveller. The inconvenient search for travel information from different data sources thus becomes unnecessary. To ensure the accessibility of airports at any time, the DORA system has to inform passengers on their travel options taking into account delays, road closures and any other kind of disruptions that might occur on the way to the airport. The general goals of DORA project are:

- Seamless connection of air transport with landside transport
- Reduction of total travel time for intra-European air travels
- Accessibility of airports at any time, even in case of disruptions
- Optimized real-time information on all transport modes for the entire route
- Design and implementation of necessary infrastructure, services and end-user applications
- Development of business models

The objectives of DORA project are aligned with the ITS policy framework of the European Commission promoting the establishment of a European system for multimodal transport information, management and payment by 2020 [1, 2].

1.2 Approach

In order to reach those goals, the DORA system provides passengers with seamless and time-optimised route recommendations for the entire journey based on real-time data for all parts of the trip chain. For the landside transport system DORA provides an intermodal routing service based on real-time data on all urban transport modes and services such as car, public transport, bike, walking, car sharing, bike sharing, taxi, car rentals or parking facilities. Delays, disruptions and the current traffic situation are taken into account for the route calculation. In case of incidents affecting the DORA user's planned journey to the airport, a re-routing is triggered, which proactively informs about alternative routes. For the way through the terminals the DORA user is provided with a newly developed indoor navigation system which takes into account the current location of the passenger (detected via Wi-Fi and newly developed beacon technologies) as well as real-time information on check-in counters, gates and the current waiting time at security checks which will be detected via cameras installed within DORA project. Information on the airside part of the journey will, of course, be also based on real-time data. All these partial routes are combined by the DORA door-to-door information system to route recommendations for the entire journey, also taking into account personal mobility preferences or constraints.

Figure 1: DORA Seamless Mobility Information

The DORA system will thus be implemented as a **seamless** solution considering scheduled and real-time information on

- all urban transport modes and mobility services
- relevant terminal proceedings (luggage belts, check-in counters, gates, security checks)
- all suitable flight connections

Furthermore the DORA system is an **integrated** solution by providing a single user interface for all travel information and services such as

- route recommendations for the entire door to door journey
- booking and ticketing for landside transport (car sharing, public transport, parking facilities)
- guidance and navigation (landside and terminal side, re-routing in case of disruptions, strategic routing in cooperation with traffic control centres)
- personalized services (different routing criteria, preferences, mobility constraints)

The DORA system will be implemented and tested in realistic environments in the cities of Berlin and Palma de Mallorca as well as their corresponding airports involving end users – air travellers - in the trials.

2. Existing solutions and added value of DORA

2.1 Existing mobility information services for air travellers

Several existing mobility information services can be identified that provide travel and routing information for air passengers. Most of these services already containing some functions of the targeted DORA system can be divided into two main groups: Intermodal long-distance trip planning services (browser-based services and/or mobile applications) and mobile applications published by airport operators.

Intermodal long-distance trip planning services are characterized by providing users with route suggestions combining different modes of transportation for interurban and intra-European connections. Whereas some trip planning services only show city to city connections for long-distance trips some more advanced services combine urban and interurban transport information to a full door to door route suggestion. Examples for full door to door trip planning services that should be mentioned are *Google Maps* and *Rome2Rio*. These two trip planning services provide traffic

information for both long-distance and local transportation and combine this data to door to door route recommendations. Both services offer train, car and flight connections for long-distance connections as well as car, public transport, bike, and walking for urban transportation. Additional urban mobility options such as taxi, car sharing or bike sharing are not included. Real-time public transport information is available only for a few cities.

For the group of mobile applications published by airport operators it can be stated that they are the most closely existing solutions to the targeted DORA system as they partly provide information for the landside part of the trip chain, for processes inside the terminal as well as detailed flight information. However, the quality and extent of mobility information in the apps of the major European airports vary significantly. A feature that all these apps provide is dynamic information on flight departures and arrivals at the airport. Indoor localization and navigation taking into account real-time data such as gate status and waiting time is only provided by very few airport apps. Landside mobility information is in many apps only static and routing services are only implemented in a simple manner (mostly with app-to-website links to Google Maps), if at all. In a market analysis of major European airport apps at the start of DORA project, the mobile applications of Vienna and Copenhagen airports were identified as the ones with the widest extent of mobility information.

2.2 Added value of the DORA system

For the comparison of the DORA system to existing intermodal long-distance trip planning services it can be noted that the existing services vary significantly in terms of provided routing functions, targeted user groups, integrated modes of transport or regional focus. The more complex ones provide intermodal door to door route recommendations based on real-time data for a remarkable number of transport modes. Nonetheless even those services do not contain the full range of seamless mobility information that will be provided by DORA. The existing services for instance fail to consider terminal processes for the planning of a door to door trip. By providing precise information about indoor terminal mobility and processes the DORA system will contribute towards reducing the overall trip duration in comparison to the described long-distance routing systems. Another added value of DORA is the integrated incident management for airport accessibility. If there are disruptions on the recommended route (street, public transport, terminal) the DORA system will inform the user accordingly and integrate this information in the routing. Additionally, only a few of the existing trip planners integrate real-time traffic information for their routing. Being informed about possible delays of public transport or traffic congestion on the highways to the airport is a crucial aspect for arriving at the airport on time and for the reliability of the proposed route. The existing trip planners also lack customized mobility information for special user groups such as business travellers, families or mobility-impaired people.

A state of the art review of existing airport apps at the beginning of DORA project has shown that even those apps which include a wide range of mobility data still lack travel information that should ideally be provided to air travellers such as real-time car and public transport routing services or waiting time information. A major difference of DORA to the existing airport apps is that a seamless

door to door route can be calculated whereas airport apps only integrate local mobility information and do not provide city to city connections. Furthermore the focus of airports apps is on terminal processes, airport infrastructure and flight information whereas the information on the journey to and from the airport is very limited in most cases.

Altogether, the existing services and solutions partly provide a wide variety of mobility information focussing on air travel but lack many functions that will be developed and integrated in DORA project. Existing intermodal long-distance trip planners usually do not give detailed information on airport or flight specific topics, airport apps, in turn, fail to provide door to door connections and landside routing functions. The added value of the targeted DORA system can be thus summarized under the following aspects:

- seamless mobility information from door to door
- consideration of real-time data for all parts of the trip chain
- integration of terminal processes by developing indoor location, navigation and waiting time detection technology
- trip monitoring and incident management
- customized mobility information
- Integrated ticketing functions

3. Technical components of the DORA system

In order to achieve the full DORA system, different components have to be developed and implemented which include backend services, end-user applications and new hardware to be installed at the airports. Figure 2 illustrates the overall concept of how the services to be implemented support seamless mobility information for air travellers.

The DORA travel chain can be divided into five major parts. The landside transport part in Berlin, the terminal part in Berlin, the actual flight part of the trip, as well as the terminal and the landside transport part in Palma de Mallorca. For each part of the trip chain there are dedicated routing services providing the respective partial routes. For the landside transport part in Berlin the partial route is calculated by the Berlin instance of the DORA Intermodal Landside Router. Different connection points at the airports (e.g. parking facilities, public transport stations, and taxi stands) determine where the routing is taken over by the indoor routing instances of Berlin and Palma that integrate real-time waiting time information and the data of the indoor localization technology. The Flight Routing Service provides the route information for the airside part of each overall door to door-route. The partial routes are combined to overall route recommendations by the Door to Door Journey Planner. This information is finally provided to the DORA user via one of the end-user applications.

Figure 2: DORA System Overview

3.1 Door to Door Journey Planner

The core service in the DORA system will be a seamless and integrated Door to Door Journey Planner which integrates existing transport mode specific real-time information services in one single intermodal routing platform for air- and landside transport. This service provides the DORA user with the optimal door-to-door route to a given cost function. For the calculation of the overall route the Door to Door Journey Planner integrates the three DORA routing services for the landside, the terminal and the flight part of the trip. It combines the results of these three routing services to suitable door to door route suggestions. The route calculation also takes into account personal mobility preferences so that individual requirements of passengers and specific user groups, for instance mobility impaired people, travelling families or business travellers, can be met. The Door to Door Journey Planner finally provides the route suggestions to the DORA frontends.

3.2 DORA end user applications

In DORA project different end user applications are being developed including a mobile, a browser-based as well as a smartwatch application. These applications enable the end users to interact with the DORA system and to receive seamless mobility information for the door to door route. The requirement engineering was based on user surveys of air passengers at Berlin and Palma de Mallorca

airports. The landside routes as well as the selected indoor route inside the terminal buildings are shown in a map to support the orientation of the passenger. A trip monitoring service supervises the selected route. In case of disruptions the user receives a push notification and a re-routing is triggered. The applications also support integrated booking and ticketing functions for the landside part of the trip (public transport, car sharing, parking). The route calculation is initially started when the DORA user requests a door to door route and selects among multiple routing parameters such as start and arrival time, departure, destination, transport modes to be considered, personal mobility constraints or cost functions (time, price, CO₂-emissions).

3.3 Operation Center Application

To make sure that the seamless mobility information of the DORA system is consistent with the local existing information services and strategies of public transport operators or airports, the operation centres of these stakeholders are cross-linked and integrated with the DORA platform. In case of incidents or disruptions, real time information services can achieve a high benefit, if incident information strategies exist and if these strategies are linked to the end user information systems. By realizing an operation centre application for cooperative incident and information management, DORA introduces an instrument for comprehensive airport-related traffic information. With the DORA operation centre application, the different operation centres will be enabled to jointly respond to delays and extraordinary conditions (e.g. technical breakdowns, strikes, bad weather) and employ decision and information management mechanisms that will be considered for traveller alerting and trip redesign.

3.4 Waiting time detection at airports

It is the traveller's responsibility to arrive at the airport with enough time to complete all ticketing, baggage check and security clearance procedures but the waiting times at check-in and security control are often not predictable. To handle this, DORA project will design and implement a waiting time detection system in the test sites' airports based on image recognition. The detected information is processed by the DORA routing platform and corresponding end-user applications for route optimisation. To ensure privacy of the passengers and employees in the airports, the video observation procedures will be fully anonymised without possibility to recognise individuals on the images.

3.5 Indoor positioning and navigation

In DORA project different innovative technologies for indoor localisation will be explored and implemented. The DORA solution will be based on existing Wi-Fi beacon frames in the airports and new installed Bluetooth Low Energy Beacons (BLE). The indoor location concept in DORA involves the development of both hardware and software components. A newly developed indoor navigation service will lead passengers through the terminals based on the detected current position. The indoor routing takes into account real-time data on current waiting times, gates, check-in counters and availability of elevators. Other airport infrastructure such as shops or restaurants is integrated as static

Points of Interests (POI). In order to guarantee for a seamless door to door routing, the indoor navigation service will start the navigation from where air travellers arrive at the airport such as parking facilities, public transport stations or taxi stands and will lead the passengers to the very gate of their flight.

4. Architectural Approach and Open APIs

In order to achieve an efficient and open system which can be transferred easily to other European cities, different requirements towards the architecture and the Application Programming Interfaces (API) of the DORA system have to be considered. Following these requirements, an initial system architecture has been compiled which will be further elaborated.

4.1 Architecture Requirements

A major priority in this project is the integration approach. DORA will enable to integrate any relevant local existing data, services and components into the system. Another important objective is to develop an open and interoperable platform which allows the adaption of new service providers on the backend site and the provision of the DORA services to DORA and third-party frontends (browser-based and mobile applications) via open interfaces. Following this approach, the platform will be transferable to other cities and airports and able to support an easy integration of existing local routing services and data. The platform and its integrated services are designed to be flexible enough to react to current system inquiries for load balancing and scalability reasons. The entire approach follows the use of ITS standards (EU and de facto standards) and, of course, European data security and privacy guidelines. Thus, the DORA architecture will be

- open: DORA provides open interfaces for applications and service providers
- distributed: integration of local data and local services
- scalable: n cities with m airports can be connected to DORA
- transferable: easy implementation of the whole DORA system or single DORA components for other cities and airports
- reliable: the functionality of the system should not depend on a single critical access point
- polymorphic: all integrated city nodes in the DORA platform should offer the same interfaces so that DORA applications can be developed with any technology and the DORA applications are interoperable with all nodes.

4.2 DORA draft architecture

Based on the mentioned requirements a draft DORA architecture has been developed. The DORA architecture basically consists of three layers: local city nodes, a service platform and end-user applications.

In Berlin and Palma de Mallorca test sites, as well as in many other major cities, real-time data and services related to landside transport like local modal routing services are already integrated in existing city platforms. These locally available system resources will be integrated in so-called DORA

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City Nodes. These City Nodes are characterized by being locally hosted and operated, e. g. in the project’s test sites. If there is an existing city platform which has already integrated the local transport information, the whole platform can be integrated in the City Node. If not, the different service and routing providers can be integrated individually. In addition, the services that will be implemented as a new part of the airport infrastructure are located in the City Node. This especially refers to the Waiting Time Detection service which, for security reasons, has to run on local servers of the airport. Finally, the City Nodes contain the local DORA Incident and Information Management Systems since they will be operated by local Traffic Control Centres.

The DORA service platform contains all central, not site specific DORA services, that contribute to the route calculation, information and monitoring. Unlike the City Nodes the DORA service platform can be located in a cloud environment since it is independent from local infrastructure and hardware. Figure 3 shows the City Nodes, the service platform and how they are interrelated. The service platform is connected to the City Nodes via the DORA Open Service API. Over this interface the central platform services receive the local data and services required for the door-to-door route calculation and information from the City Nodes. The indoor router and the landside router, for instance, receive the required waiting time detection data and the local mobility information respectively via the Open Service API. This architecture and open API approach facilitates the addition of other City Nodes to the DORA system in the future.

Figure 3: DORA City Nodes and Service Platform

Different applications will be connected to the DORA System as shown in figure 4. These include a Web-GUI, mobile applications, a smartwatch application as well as an Operation Centre Application. All applications, both internal and third-party applications, communicate with the DORA service platform and the DORA City Nodes over the Open Application API. This interface is especially designed to meet the requirements that applications have regarding communication processes. Over

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this API to the DORA service platform the applications request and receive the central door-to-door information provided by the Door-to-Door Journey Planner. From the City Nodes the applications receive, for instance, detailed information on specific POIs of a route, for example on relevant car-sharing vehicles or parking facilities.

Figure 4: Connection of Applications to the DORA System

4.3 DORA Open Protocols

The DORA Open Protocols (Service API and Application API) will be developed within the project and will support an easy integration of additional City Nodes into the DORA system and of DORA services into third-party applications. They will provide a state of the art open data exchange format for mobility services and applications. The specification of the protocols will be available in April 2016. The interfaces need to be self-evident, well documented and easy to understand and will be based on existing standards if possible. If an additional City Node, single service or application is supposed to be connected to the DORA system, the implementation of the DORA Open Protocols is required. Automatic system tests for all DORA functions need to be implemented and successfully passed by newly-included applications or services in order to guarantee for a high quality of the overall system.

4. Business framework and exploitation approach

DORA as a platform-based information system for traveling optimization functions as an ecosystem where several players across industries work together to collaboratively create and distribute value for multiple customer groups [3, 4], i.e. air passengers and mobility operators. Business models typically define how an individual organization creates, delivers and captures value considering critical factors

related to economic (sources of revenues and costs), business architecture, value proposition and value chain position. However, in ecosystem-based business (such as DORA) the value is created in collaboration with various partners and the captured value needs to be redistributed among the partners in a fair and equitable way, respectful of the partners' contribution to the ecosystem and its further development [5]. Platforms compete for members and customers on the basis of platform quality, indirect network effects, and consumer expectations [6]. The various involved parties' decision to connect or adopt the ecosystem is highly linked to value appropriation (the individual share of each actor from the value created) i.e. value capture enabled by the chosen business model.

As a technological solution DORA generates value in multiple ways: financial benefits (via cost savings and revenue), societal benefits (greener, more efficient use of public transport), added use of transport services, prevention and mitigation of disruptive events etc. This generated value is considerable in total but divided unevenly across the involved stakeholders, as are also the costs of maintaining the system in operation. For DORA the core issue is thus to manage the collaboration of an ecosystem of multiple types (e.g. cities, airports, airlines, private and public transport operators) of actors in an open innovation relationship. The success of the platform is dependent on its ability to first attract a critical mass of each key stakeholder type, and then sustain their commitment. On the longer run, incentivizing innovation becomes critical as well. Thus, it is critical to balance the value generated for, and captured by, the various parties so that the total value generated by the network is maximized and each actor captures sufficient value to incentivize ongoing commitment and investment. Otherwise key stakeholders may switch to competitors, reaching critical adoption will become prohibitively costly and continued innovation of the platform and its services will be stifled - as has been the case with countless platforms that have failed to realize their potential.

Both the value creation and value capture aspects introduce specific requirements for sustaining a multi-sided platform-based system. The business framework for the DORA platform will be developed in stages to allow for and incentivize increasing levels of adoption and feature integration. In the heart of DORA business model is the core solution including the most crucial actors (passenger, airports, airlines, transport operators) and features (e.g. development of software and secure information flows). Here, the sustainable balance of value generated and captured by key stakeholders is managed by defining acceptable revenue streams and redistribution schemes and defining orchestration and ownership responsibility on the platform level. These elements constitute the basic DORA business framework. After successful establishment of the core DORA business solution, additional features may be implemented. This means integration of new stakeholders such as airport shops, cities, information centers etc. DORA offers also possibilities to the integration to other already established platforms (such as Tripadvisor). These will add further possibilities for creating value and capturing it which will in turn be planned for and managed in additional stages building on top of the basic framework. The project has initiated the business model definition by gathering requirements and expectations from the key stakeholders in an expert workshop in January 2016 with the final dynamic, networked business framework for exploitation to be completed in November 2016

5. Conclusion

The DORA system is aimed at reducing travel time for intra-European connections by providing air travellers with seamless door-to-door mobility information. Since existing solutions in this field do not provide a satisfactory compilation of routing functions and mobility information, the seamless and integrated approach of DORA is supposed to fill this gap and enable air travellers to make informed decisions, receive personalised route recommendations, and arrive at the final destination of a trip conveniently and on-time. To reach those goals different system components are developed and integrated. Existing local mobility information and routing services are bundled in the so-called City Nodes as the main data source on which the DORA system will be based on. Technologies for indoor positioning and waiting time detection are developed and installed at the airports in order to improve the navigation through the terminals. New developed DORA services located in a central platform provide the route calculation and trip monitoring functions to the system. As the core service the Door to Door Journey Planner combines the partial routes for the landside, the terminal and the airside parts of the journey to suitable seamless route recommendations. The routing results are presented to users in different DORA frontends being developed such as a mobile, a smartwatch and a browser-based application. The system architecture with its open API approach is designed in a way that the whole system or single components can be easily transferred to other cities and airports and integrated into third-party applications.

The modular and distributed approach of DORA also supports the development of different business models suited to the requirements of different stakeholders. Whereas some stakeholders might be interested in the whole DORA system, others might only see an added value in one single component. As DORA generates value in multiple ways there are manifold points of reference for developing business solutions.

After the start of the project in June 2015, all use cases and technical requirements have been collected and aligned. The DORA architecture including the open APIs has been successfully defined. The software development and integration process starts in April 2016.

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